

Mahesh Sharma:

**Deconstructing the Ethical and the Political in
Postcolonial Hospitality**

**Postcolonial Interventions: An Interdisciplinary
Journal of Postcolonial Studies**

ABSTRACT:

The present condition of globalization has created a unique predicament for the postcolonial society. Those who were once colonized have come face to face with their colonizers resulting in making a new postcolonial dyad of guest/host. Hospitality provides for the possibility of coexistence and assimilation. But this is possible only if we leave the question of identity aside, rather than latching on to it. Assimilation is a fundamental need for society today, which will create a community and it is also desirable in a community. Deconstruction of hospitality is an absolute aporia as two things try to function together – the unconditional hospitality which is sought by asylum seekers, refugees, and former colonized peoples, and on the other hand the risk and internal conflicts that hospitality carries with it, that of a risk to its own citizens. The flow of people into the host country is inescapably restrained and limited at the political and subjective levels. There is a double bind in hospitality – one which acknowledges risks and the other which is vigilant. An ethics of negotiation is necessary to reach the limits of a normative unconditional hospitality.

Derrida's deconstructionist approach to hospitality creates an aporia within the concept of hospitality. The stranger, the host, the immigrant, the asylum seeker, the refugee all need to be in a balance, which is the condition of possibility for unconditional hospitality. For Derrida, hospitality should be unconditional which is to say nothing should come in the way of taking the decision of inviting or accepting the guest. The present paper discusses the notion of Derrida's hostipitality (hostility + hospitality) to understand the contemporary postcolonial condition of conviviality.

Keywords- *Guest/Host, Colonizer/Colonized, Hostipitality, Derrida, Cosmopolitanism, Postcolonial Discourse*

The common definition of hospitality is the relationship the host has with the guest, which includes welcoming the guest or stranger and treating him as equal. Care and providing for his/her needs are part of the practice. Hospitality to a stranger is different from welcoming a friend or a family member where the person does not necessarily need to be welcomed – here the other feels part of the host and can live with the host freely, without constraints. As Derrida points out, “all ethics of hospitality are not the same ... there is no culture or social bond without a principle of hospitality” (Principles of Hospitality 6). The practice of hospitality changes with socio-cultural practices. The guest feels that he is a stranger from the moment of hospitality, when he does not know what to do next. He feels other even when the host tries to assimilate him. Julian Pitt-Rivers further explains “as a newcomer he will never know from the outset how to behave towards individual personalities... but to fulfill the role of guest he must at least understand the conventions which relate to hospitality and which define the behaviour expected of him” (The Law of Hospitality 504). Derrida’s concept of ‘hostipitality’ (hostility + hospitality) captures the essence of the agonistic pluralist approach among various poles which maintain such a relation (of ‘hostipitality’) without claiming superiority (*On Cosmopolitanism and Forgiveness*). Kant argues that the principle of ‘hospitality’, “the right of a stranger not to be treated with hostility when he arrives on someone else’s territory” (Kant, *Political Writings* 105), plays an important factor in propagating the Kantian cosmopolitan space where perpetual peace will prevail through the practice of “principles of justice among free and democratic people” (135). Derrida’s concepts of the singular and the universal nevertheless make the understanding of hospitality in today’s world politics easier. I go on to show that friendship is an essential criterion of an ethics of hospitality as defined by Derrida, and how in postcolonial hospitality the unconditional has to be even more present in the practical politics of border crossing. I will finally deal with hospitality as cosmopolitanism, in which the notion of responsibility is deeply rooted. The ethics of

hospitality is explained through these different terms, which are normative preconditions that can guide politics towards being ethical in the cosmopolitan scenario, at least theoretically, even if it cannot be practiced as such.

Deconstruction deals with writing as well as with metaphysics. The linguistic “turn” from the traditional conception of language towards metaphysics changed the structural configuration of the Western tradition and challenged logocentricism. Derrida defines deconstruction as “hospitality to the other” (*Interruptions* 4), reinforcing the latter as a traditional concept where the host (the innkeeper) waits for whoever passes by his home and needs a shelter, whether it is an animal, human or God, and gives it without questioning. (This practice in today’s world order seems impossible due to multiple problems such as immigration, increase in the number of asylum seekers and illegal refugees).

Guest-Host Dichotomy

The guest-host relationship can be extended beyond humans alone – it can be between humans and animals, and between humans and God. This latter is the traditional concept of hospitality where the guest, whoever it is, must be welcomed, because the guest might be ‘God in disguise’. Therefore, in some traditions such as in India, guests are treated like God – *atithidevobhava*. The host must go beyond the limit to fulfill the needs of the guest, treating the Other as oneself. This is why the Other can never remain the Other, he becomes part of the Self. As Derrida would say, the Other must collapse into the same (2000, 2001). This is the mystery that lies at the root of hospitality – the host confronts the unknown stranger who is mysterious. The ambiguity of their positions can either culminate in hostility or hospitality, and this depends on the status of each individually. For the former not to take place, the host and guest can never be equal. If this is the

case, the latter (hospitality) in Derrida's conception can never take place because the ethics of hospitality function when it is unconditional, where the host and the guest are one and the same.

This practice of hospitality has several problems, one of which is the possibility of the host becoming hostage. There are several ways in which this is possible. Firstly, the law of hospitality presumes that the host has to take care of the guest and fulfill all his needs. In this case, the host becomes hostage to the law of hospitality where he cannot escape it; at the same time, he also becomes hostage to the guest whom he also has to obey. Secondly, the host becomes hostage when the guest crosses his limits and space as a guest and starts demanding and dominating over the host. In both cases the "host" is both the host and the hostage, but at different levels.

The law of hospitality is to be dealt with, in contrast to codes of hospitality as seen in different cultures. There are natural laws of hospitality that are derived from sociological necessities. For example, the host must not be insulted, usurped, or infringed upon, for otherwise rivalry ensues. The guest must always remain within his limits, failing which hospitality is transformed into hostility. For this not to take place, the guest must always remain the Other and follow the rules of the host, and they must live together as two distinct categories. Unlike what Derrida says, I think that the host must live autonomously as a subjective self and not give him/herself to the guest. For Derrida, although these are two distinct entities, they must live as one with unconditional hospitality – where the Other is treated as the same without negotiating the priority of the host (2000, 2005). Although his approach is ethical and takes hospitality to its ultimate im-possibility, there are some problems which it can lead to, especially in world politics. (I use the term im-possible with a hyphen to distinguish it from impossible without a hyphen, to show that the former may lead to a possibility, whereas for the latter there is no possibility.)

There is also a third condition to the host-guest relationship, as in the case of the U.S., which is known as a country of immigrants. The citizens of the U.S were formerly guests who pushed out

the indigenous people of that land and claimed to have discovered it, and therefore viewed it as belonging to them. In this case, the indigenous people who should have been the host as they inhabited that territory could not do so. Although the ‘host’ and the ‘guest’ were present there, they did not have the relation determined by the laws of hospitality – a major issue in the ethics of hospitality. In such situations, can settler countries like the U.S ever be the host to citizens from another country? Do they hold the same status as, say in Japan or U.K, or any other country which are not settler countries? Is their “hospitality” different from that of the rest? To answer these politically charged questions, the concept of the responsibility that one feels for another is important. Not only must it function at the political level but also at the ethical level.

In *The Origins of Responsibility*, François Raffoul rightly says that there have been new perspectives on ethics with the proliferation of a philosophical outlook towards ethics rather than a view of it as a practical discipline. For an ethics of hospitality to take place in everyday politics, it is essential to study ethics first in a normative body: “There is no need to ‘add’ an ethics as an applied discipline to an ontology which would then have been presupposed as unethical” (3). Unlike Raffoul, the normative framework built by theorists such as Derrida, Levinas, Heidegger, Nancy and others on ethics believe that it is essential for ethics to be present in the politics of hospitality. Although for Derrida as well as for Raffoul this approach would be unethical, Derrida says that it is this impossibility of the ethics which they suggest is the basis for creating a possibility for the application of ethics: “ethical judgment ... becomes only possible from such groundlessness” (6). Although practically it seems impossible, there is a need for terms such as hospitality, responsibility, ethics, politics, international relations, immigration, etc. to be theorized, and such a background must be created so that there is a “possible” created within the “im-possible”.

In an attempt to go beyond the general conception of the politics and ethics of hospitality, recent studies have focused on subjects as different as the host and the guest in relation to the Self

and the Other, deconstruction as hospitality, friendship as essential to hospitality, the role of the community in this dialectics, the position of the postcolonial subject face-to-face with his former colonisers, and the function of hospitality in a global scenario like cosmopolitanism. While some researchers have dealt with hospitality from a realist perspective, others have sought to show how hospitality is aporetic and (im)possible. Mireille Rosello (2001) suggests that ideally, the definition of hospitality should change according to the “type of journey”, but this is not actually the case. While the laws of hospitality are the same for all, there have been instances in history where one community was privileged over the other; where hospitality should have been a mutual benevolence, there has been a suspicion in the relation between the host and the guest.

In extensive studies of aporia in hospitality, theorists such as Derrida, Mark W. Westmoreland and others have supported the necessity of unconditional hospitality as a condition of possibility for a global community. The need for practicing Derrida’s unconditional hospitality is developed by Judith Still (2010) from an interdisciplinary framework which is key to her work in which sexual difference is one of the strands in the study of hospitality. What is of interest in her work is her influence on postcolonial studies in the complex relations between France and Algeria. Unlike Derrida who demands a balance and situates his work in pure theory. Still her work *Derrida and Hospitality: Theory and Practice* puts forth an empirical framework which gives her writing and interpretation more flexibility and scope. In discussing the issue of hospitality in sexual difference, she incorporates the works of other women like Helene Cixous and Judith Butler. Nevertheless, she does not consider discussing the issues of those who have written on colonization and who have fought with their people for independence such as Albert Memmi, who has also extensively written on the issue of hospitality and assimilation.

Her chapter on friendship, which she develops from Derrida’s essay “Politics of Friendship”, traces friendship as a sexual relation, unlike Derrida who has an obsessive demand that the friend is

the same as the Self. Going back in the line of the Western philosophical tradition, Aristotle states that good legislation is directed by friendship rather than by justice, and is beyond any code of law. Friendship is the first law of community without which no government or law can exist. While Derrida states that friendship is a detached practice and exists in death, where there is no distinction between the Self and the friend, Giorgio Agamben conceives of friendship as a first step towards alterity, an experience which makes ‘oneself’ exist without being reduced to the ‘same’. The friend makes you discover yourself at the same time as putting your identity into question, which Agamben says is friendship’s greatest gift. This perspective is essential in relating oneself to the Other and to the community.

Hospitality in general and cosmopolitan ethics in particular is considered from the standpoint of a universal democracy – a universality which impinges on the freedom and rights of humanism. This approach has several problems, including among others the denial of individuality or singularity. Derrida’s perspective on hospitality is derived from the works of Kant on cosmopolitan rights, which although seemingly universal, are limited to the rights of visitors in the European context. What Derrida does is to seek hospitality in the post-Enlightenment era, going beyond these limits, moving towards cosmopolitanism, where the stranger or foreigner is unconditionally welcomed, where the Other remains his/herself without collapsing into the Self. This approach makes assimilation easier and Derrida’s ethics of hospitality is seen from a position of singularity rather than multiplicity (*Politics of Friendship* 23).

It is from this perspective that Derrida speaks about a “democracy to come” (*Rogues: Two Essays on Reason*). A basic normative framework is necessary and is a precondition for future cosmopolitan justice, and the initiative taken up by intellectuals, writers, and those men and women who have the potential to voice their opinion for a world unity –cosmopolitanism – is a step towards this apparently utopic conception. Nevertheless, this seemingly messy and confusing process of

hospitality and what Derrida calls a “ville-refuge” is essential to attain the international rights which all human beings possess (*On Cosmopolitanism and Forgiveness* 18). A new state politics is sought.

From the normative notion of hospitality as propounded by Derrida, one can derive that in today’s world order; unconditional hospitality is not just possible but is a necessary precondition for a better global reason to function. Take the example of Sweden’s migration and asylum policy, which gave asylum seekers the right to live in Sweden on humanitarian grounds; it has been questioned after the May 2013 riots between the indigenous people and refugees due to lack of integration despite the government’s efforts. This is an (im)possibility of unconditional hospitality; that is to say, border crossing must be limited and all those who are part of this limit must be welcomed unconditionally. After a person has been permitted to cross borders, he must be treated as equal to the indigenous people without constraints.

The ethics of hospitality is possible only in the presence of a politics of hospitality. Without the latter, the former cannot exist. How can the ethics of hospitality take place if there is no politics? What is the politics of hospitality? What role does ethics play in the political practice of hospitality? To answer these questions, we need to turn to Derrida’s approach to hospitality to see what kind of hospitality is necessary for an ethical politics of hospitality. Derrida’s ethics of hospitality will create the possibility for a better world politics.

Derrida’s deconstructionist approach to hospitality creates an aporia within the concept of hospitality. The stranger, the host, the immigrant, the asylum seeker, the refugee all need to be in a balance, which is the condition of possibility for unconditional hospitality. For Derrida, hospitality should be unconditional which is to say nothing should come in the way of taking the decision of inviting or accepting the guest. The guest knows he is waiting for someone but does not know who it is. “He [the host] waits without waiting. He waits without knowing whom he awaits” (“Hostipitality”, 10). The stranger remains a stranger until he is named as such. If somebody is called a stranger, there

is already a relation between the two – the host and the stranger – and therefore s/he is not a stranger any more. He becomes either a friend or an enemy or simply an existing entity. Aporia lies within the concept of the “known stranger” and the “unknown stranger”. The principle of hospitality demands welcoming the “stranger” without limits. But there is a problem in welcoming, in letting the stranger into one’s home, for with the unconditional welcome there is a possibility that one’s home will be threatened by the newcomer.

Unconditional hospitality is not bound by any laws or code of conduct and the person who arrives lives as freely as does the indigenous, and therefore both the host and the newcomer lose their status. Hospitality necessitates the presence of a host and the visitor, but in the case of unconditional hospitality they do not exist. Unconditional hospitality therefore defies the laws of hospitality as the host does not anymore remain the host. It is hospitality which both passively resists and welcomes the guest in different forms.

For hospitality to be possible, the host as well as the Other need to be present and the host must maintain the status of the patron of the household. This Other, in the case of unconditional hospitality, can always be a threat for the host as both become equals and the Other can take over the host and begin to rule the home. Therefore hostility comes along with hospitality to safeguard the home, a concept for which Derrida coined the term “hostipitality”, wherein both the words ‘hospitality’ and ‘hostility’ exist simultaneously.

In a recent incident in Italy, three Italian girls were fined for wearing swimsuits on a beach in Italy (which is their own country) in front of some Saudi Arabian tourist. This action of the girls hurt the Muslim religious sentiments and a case was filed against them with the help of the Sharia Law, wherein the court of Italy equated them to prostitutes and the girls were fined a sum of \$3,500 each (www.jewsnews.co.il). Do visitors have the right to file such cases in their visiting country because of cultural difference? Here we see that it is due to religious intolerance that the Muslim visitors over-

stepped their rights and the permission that was given to them by the Italian government, and accused three girls who were well within their cultural practices. What is more surprising is that the court in Italy took sides with these visitors and condemned the girls. Why did the government not take sides with their own people in spite of being well aware of their cultural practices? This is one of the cases (amongst others) where hospitality has bred hostility between the guest and the host. Can stopping Muslim visitors entering into their country be a solution for problems like this? Or must the host country continue having visitors because of the basic rights people have of visiting another country? There can be no one answer to such kinds of problems.

Conditions and laws for immigration are obligatory to maintain the structure of a nation. The politics of hospitality in border crossing are maintained by contracts such as the passport, immigration laws and laws of citizenship. These terms are generally conceived as purely political and are practiced for beneficial and selfish reasons. Today the world demands hospitality as responsibility on ethical grounds. Nations are seeking an ethics which can function beyond nationalism, which Derrida seems to comprehend and conceptualize as unconditional hospitality. Calling a person an immigrant, a refugee etc. is already fixing an identity and putting a law and a specific understanding of and towards the other into place. These names are given only after the status of the other is known through questioning and then categorized. There are several barriers to this politics, one of which is language. Comprehension is not always possible across nations due to differences in language, but translation can erase this lack, and it is thus necessary for hospitality (“Hostipitality” 6).

Understanding the Postcolonial Hospitality

Does the notion of hospitality change in postcolonial context? Does it set aside the host-guest relationship because of the history of colonial violence? It is different from the hospitality which I have explained above, because this hospitality is preceded by a history of violence, terror, torture and

years of colonization. In this section, I attempt to show that the hosts owe their former colonies an unconditional hospitality, as they have been wrongly treated, violently taken over and disowned from their identities as a people. Derrida in *Of Hospitality* seeks to answer the question ‘where does hospitality begin?’ Answering this question in the postcolonial context rather than in the general framework of hospitality, I think postcolonial hospitality begins from the beginning of the process of colonization.

The future host and the guest had a relation even before entering into these categories. Rosello in her book *Postcolonial Hospitality* demonstrates the representation of hospitality in France and in African colonies especially in Algeria. What dominates the concept of the host and the guest is a sense of nationalism. She questions the oblivion of the settler colonies and the former empire by stating that the settlers have forgotten what they have taken from the indigenous people who used to live in that territory before. She also discusses why some forms of hospitality are privileged over the other and explains the different conflicts existing between hospitalities, where some are considered dangerous, illegal or irresponsible. She explores how language is the cause of inhospitality to migrants. The undecidability in Derrida’s work or rather in works that use deconstructive practices are often considered irresponsible.

One of the major points which Rosello fails to discuss is that hospitality comes with the responsibility the host has to feel responsible towards its former colonies. In this case hospitality might be comparatively more restrained due to the fear of revenge and the former colonies’ fight for justice. But in practice the contrary should be right, where the host should do anything they can in order to pay back for their misdeeds.

Language plays an essential role in postcolonial hospitality. Taking the example of France and its colonies especially Algeria, the latter have adopted, or more correctly, French has been imposed upon them as an official language. In this case, hospitality may be considered as coming

from the other side – that is Algeria has been hospitable to France by using French which can be understood by those living in France. Using a language that does not belong to them in order to communicate with the other can be perceived as lending a hand to the stranger and making communication possible, unlike the methods used by the host (France) where translation is necessary to understand one another.

Labeling is and has always been an essential part of immigration policies, where the identity of the immigrant is first questioned and then judged by the host, and only then a decision is taken. Is judging the future immigrant only on the basis of name, religion, language and history ethical? By doing this, isn't there an imposition of the identity of the potential immigrant's fellow companions (who might have done something wrong in the past) on the person who is being questioned? Immigration from former colonies, says Ben Jelloun, necessitates both rights and duties and must be done within the legal framework, which I believe negates ethics as responsibility. In this situation an ethics of (unconditional) hospitality should be preceded by an ethics of responsibility. At the same time, Derrida's umbrella term hostipitality, which is also always present in this situation leaves open the condition of possibility for attacking the host and taking over his position.

Refugees and homeless people seek a different politics of international border crossing which goes beyond the interest of the host country, the city or the nation-state. Taking the case of Algeria and its former colonizer in today's world order, we see that during and after colonization there have been a lot of people crossing borders between these two countries – they were either forced into it, or did it willfully. Nevertheless, they have been separated from their roots and have had to adopt another mode of life. In the case of the French living in Algeria, the question of them offering hospitality to others does not arise because they have settled in Algeria forcefully, without having been invited, and have taken over the Algerians. They therefore cannot call Algeria their home into which they can

invite someone. To maintain hospitality, the person has to be first the host and own or possess the house. Without this the question of hospitality does not arise.

Deconstruction of hospitality is an absolute aporia as two things try to function together – the unconditional hospitality which is sought by asylum seekers, refugees, and formerly colonized peoples, and on the other hand the risk and internal conflicts that hospitality carries with it, that of a risk to its own citizens. The flow of people into the host country is inescapably restrained and limited at the political and subjective levels. There is a double bind in hospitality – one which acknowledges risks and the other which is vigilant. An ethics of negotiation is necessary to reach the limits of a normative unconditional hospitality.

In the end, the tension in Derrida's thought centers on the issue of normativity. On the one hand, a genuine decision cannot depend upon established norms; every decision must be ultimately haunted by undecidability. On the other hand, unconditional hospitality appears as a law, it forcefully puts into question conditional laws of hospitality; it works to create a new cosmo-politics; and yet unconditional hospitality, like justice, is not a law (a 'thing') but rather a call or claim (Bonney 80).

Aporia does not stop an action; rather it forces one to respond to unconditional hospitality at the same time acknowledging the risk. Derrida used three phrases concerning hospitality, which are: *ethics is hospitality*, *ethics as hospitality* and *politics of hospitality*. The "is" in the first phrase makes it unconditional and universal, while the other two are conditional, contingent and complementary. "While Levinas was deeply concerned by the political realities of life, his thinking of hospitality remains silent about the way in which the ethical promise it makes can be translated into politics" (Still 19)

Hospitality provides for the possibility of coexistence and assimilation. But this is possible only if we leave the question of identity aside, rather than latching on to it. Assimilation is a fundamental need for society today, which will create a community and it is also desirable in a

community. Like Derrida, for Albert Memmi also, identity must be put aside in order to understand the possibility for hospitality. This will ensure that encounters without oppositions take place. Each must recognize the other as being part of oneself. The colonizer who leaves the colony does not take everything along. Part of it is left behind which the colonized must accept. They must also accept that their identity, community, society have changed and been modified by the foreigners, and do not have to completely reject them. What they have left behind is not necessarily something bad – it can be secured to their advantage. If the colonized do not accept the remains of colonization, it will be a “self-destructive reaction to colonialism” (Memmi 208). There is also a change in language, but for Derrida this is not a big issue; he says in *Monolingualism of the Other* that all languages, cultures are hybrid and are not pure (8). They are always influenced by others around. Difference should be left aside for assimilation and hospitality.

Israel-Pelletier suggests that colonizers and colonized, host and guest have been in contact with each other for a long time and several exchanges have taken place (“Assimilation, Hospitality, and the politics of Identity in Albert Memmi”). Due to this there are more similarities than differences and thus no need of asserting one’s power and sovereignty. Just as Derrida asserts that language does not belong only to oneself and is a mix, for Memmi it is the same with identity which is not pure. Power politics, as much as it creates differences and gives a sense of nationalism, is also necessary to keep communities together.

Absolute hospitality frees you from sovereignty and the boundaries of law and politics. Both Derrida and Memmi agree that this approach is unrealistic but this seems the only way to get ethics and politics to function together. They believe that politics can never become ethical, but it is surrounded by it and there is a constant conflict between them. Nevertheless politics should not be left on its own. Although both hold a similar stand towards ethics and politics, they have different perspectives on hospitality. While Derrida talks about absolute hospitality as an ethical urgency, for

Memmi, hospitality like assimilation is a strategy for a different mode of thought of binary thinking of subjects. For him, being attached to singularity can be dangerous for assimilation and therefore for hospitality.

A thorough understanding of postcolonial subjectivity is needed to determine the tension between ethics and politics as well as the notion of guest and host. If we have to bring this deconstructive philosophy out of the closet, we all will have to develop a normative consciousness where the Other will always be respected as part of the Self.

Works Cited

Agamben, Giorgio. "Friendship." *Contretemps* 5, (2004): 2-7.. Print.

Anderson, B. *Imaginary Communities: Reflections on the Origin and Spread of Nationalism*. London: Verso. 1983. Print.

Bauman, Zygmunt. *Community: Seeking Safety in an Insecure World*. Cambridge: Polity Press, 2001. Print.

-----, *Postmodern Ethics*.UK: Blackwell Publishing, 1993. Print.

Bellah, R., Madsen, R., Sullivan, W., Swidler, A. and Tipton, S. *Habits of the Heart*. 2nd Edition. Berkeley: University of California Press, 1996. Print.

Benhabib, S. *Another Cosmopolitanism*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2008. Print.

Bonney, Nathan D. *The Risk of Hospitality: Selfhood, Otherness, and Ethics in Deconstruction and Phenomenological Hermeneutics*. Diss. 2012. Print.

Cohen, A. *The Symbolic Construction of Community*. London: Tavistock, 1985. Print.

Connolly, W. E. *The Ethos of Pluralization*. Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press, 1995. Print.

Conrad, Joseph. *Heart of Darkness*. Dover: Dover Publication House, 1902, Print.

Critchley, S. ‘The Other’s Decision in Me: (What are the Politics of Friendship?)’. *European Journal of Social Theory*, 1 (2): 259–79. 1998. Print.

Currie, Mark. *Difference*. London: Routledge, 2004. Print.

Dallmyre, Fred. *Being in the World*. Kentucky: Kentucky U P., 2013. Print.

Davis, Colin. *Levinas: An Introduction*. Ed. Donn Welton. Bloomington, Indiana: Indiana U P, 1999. Print.

Deleuze, Gilles and Felix Guattari. *Anti-Oedipus: Capitalism and Schizophrenia*. Trans. R Hurley, M. Seem and H. R. Lane. New York: Viking Press. 1977. Print.

Deleuze, Gilles. *Difference and Repetition*. Trans. P. Paton. London: Athlone Press, 1994. Print.

Derrida, Jacques, and Anne Dufourmantelle. *Of Hospitality*. Trans. Rachel Bowlby. California: Stanford UP, 2000. Print.

---. ‘Hostipitality.’ Trans. Barry Stocker and Forbes Morlock. *Angelaki: Journal of Theoretical*

Humanities 5.3 (2000): 3-18. Print

---. "Performative Powerlessness: A Response to Simon Critchley." *The Derrida- Habermas Reader*.

Ed. Lasse Thomassen. Edinburgh: Edinburgh UP, 2006. 111-14. Print.

---. "The Politics of Friendship." *American Imago* 50:3 (1993): 353-391. Print.

---. "The Principles of Hospitality." *Parallax* 11.1 (2005): 6-9. Print.

---. *Of Grammatology*. Trans. Gayatri Chakraborty Spivak. Baltimore: The Johns Hopkins University Press, 1997. Print.

---. *Positions*, Trans. Alan Bass. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 1982. Print.

-----. *Writing and Difference*. Trans. Alan Bass. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 1978. Print.

-----. *Monolingualism of the Other; or, The Prosthesis of Origin*. Trans. Patrick Mensah. Stanford: Stanford UP, 1998. Print.

-----. *On the Name*. Ed. Thomas Dutoit. Stanford: Stanford UP, 1995. Print.

---. *On Cosmopolitanism and Forgiveness*. Trans. Mark Dooley & Michael Hughes. London & New York: Routledge, 2001. Print.

Elliott, A. *Social Theory and Psychoanalysis in Transition: Self and Society from Freud to Kristeva*. London: Free Association Books, 1999. Print.

Fischer, C. "Uncommon Values, Diversity and Conflict in City Life". *Diversity and Its Discontents: Cultural Conflict and Common Ground in Contemporary American Society*. Eds. N. Smelser and J. Alexander. Princeton: Princeton University Press, 1999. Print.

Foucault, Michel. "Technologies of the Self". *Technologies of the Self: A Seminar with Michel Foucault*. Eds. L.H. Martin, H. Gutman, P.H. Hutton. London: Tavistock Publication, 1988. 16- 49. Print.

---. *Fearless Speech*. Los Angeles: Semiotext(e), [Distributed by MIT], 2001. Print.

-----. "Power." *Essential Works of Foucault 1954-1984*. By Michel Foucault. Vol. 3. New York: New Press, 2000. 326-28. Print.

---. *The Hermeneutics of the Subject*. New York: Picador, 2001. Print.

-----. *The History of Sexuality*, Vol.1. Trans. Robert Hurley. Harmondsworth: Penguin, 1981. Print.

Glendinning, Simon. *On Being with Others. Heidegger, Derrida, Wittgenstein*. New York: Routledge, 1998. Print.

Gordimer, Nadine. *Living in Hope and History*. New York: Farrar, Straus and Giroux, 1999. Print.

Hadot, Pierre. *Exercices Spirituels et Philosophie Antique*. Paris: Études Augustiniennes, 1981. Print.

-----. *What is Ancient Philosophy?* Cambridge, Mass.: The Belknap Press of Harvard University Press, 2002. Print.

Heidegger, Martin. *Being and Time*. New York: State University of New York, 1996. Print.

Hofmeyr, Benda. *Ethics and Aesthetics in Foucault and Levinas*. Nijmegen: Radbound University, J.E. Jurrianse Stichting, 2005. Print.

Husserl, David. *The Essential Husserl: Basic Writings in Transcendental Phenomenology*. Ed. Donn Welton. Bloomington, Indiana: Indiana U P, 1999. Print.

Isbister, John. "Are Immigration Controls Ethical?" *Social Justice* 23. 3 (1996): 54-67. Print.

Israel-Pelletier, Aimée. "Assimilation, Hospitality, and the politics of Identity in Albert Memmi." *French Forum* 23.1-2 (2013): 205-219. Print.

Jewsnews.co.il. "Italian Girls Fined \$3,500 each for Wearing Swimsuits Near Muslims on Italian Beach". <<http://www.jewsnews.co.il/2014/05/12/italian-girls-fined-3500-each-for-wearing-swimsuits-near-muslims-on-italian-beach/>>. Visited on May 12, 2014. Web.

Kant, Immanuel. *Political Writing*. Ed. H.S. Reiss. London: Cambridge University Press, 1991. Print.

Levinas, Emmanuel. "Ethics and Politics." *Levinas Reader*. Ed. Sean Hand. Oxford: Blackwell, 1989. 289-97. Print.

-----, *Totality and Infinity: An Essay on Exteriority*. Trans. Alphonso Lingis. Pittsburg: Duquesne University Press, 1969. Print.

Lindroos, K. 'Scattering Community: Benjamin on Experience, Narrative and History'. *Philosophy and Social Criticism*, 27 (6): 19–41. 2001. Print.

Macey, David. "Rethinking Biopolitics, Race and Power in the Wake of Foucault". *Theory, Culture and Society*. 26. 6 (2009): 186-205. Print.

Marin, Marie-Eve. *Jean-Luc Nancy*. Malden, Polity Press. 2012. Print.

Mouffe Chantal. *Agonistics*. London: Verso, 2013. Print.

Nancy, Jean-Luc. *Being Singular Plural*. Tr. R. D. Richardson and A. E. O'Byrne. Stanford: Stanford University Press, 2000 [1996]. Print.

---. *The Inoperative Community*. Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press, 1991. Print.

Parekh, B. *Rethinking Multiculturalism: Cultural Diversity and Political Theory*. London: Macmillan, 2000. Print.

Patrick, Morag. *Derrida, Responsibility and Politics*. Ashgate, 1997. Print.

Pitt-Rivers, Julian. "The Law of Hospitality." *Journal of Ethnographic Theory* 2:1 (2012): 17-28. Print.

Post, Robert. *Constitutional Domains: Democracy, Community, Management*. Cambridge, Mass: Harvard University Press, 1995. Print.

Putnam, R. *Making Democracy Work: Civic Traditions in Modern Italy*. Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press, 1993. Print.

------. *Bowling Alone*. New York: Simon & Schuster, 1999. Print.

Raffoul, Francois. *The Origins of Responsibility*. Bloomington: Indiana UP, 2010. Print.

Said, Edward. *Orientalism*. Penguin: London, 1978. Print.

Still, Judith. *Derrida and Hospitality. Theory and Practice*. Edinburgh: Edinburgh UP, 2010. Print.

Turner, V. *The Ritual Process: Structure and Anti-Structure*. London: Routledge & Kegan Paul, 1969. Print.

Wagner, P. *Theorizing Modernity*. London: Sage, 2001. Print.

Weber, Elisabeth, ed. *Living Together: Jacques Derrida's Communities of Violence and Peace*. New York: Fordham University Press, 2013. Print.

Westmoreland, Mark W. "Interruptions: Derrida and Hospitality." *Kritike*. Vol. 2:1 (2008): 1-10.

Web.